

INNOVATION MANAGEMENT: BASIC CONCEPTS AND CLASSIFICATION

Kambarova L.R. Teacher

Department of Social and Exact Sciences.

Tashkent State University of Economics, Tashkent, Republic of Uzbekistan

Email: Li26ka0695@gmail.com

Abstract

The fundamental terms "*innovation*" and the primary categories of innovations included in the classification table are defined in the article along with the steps of the innovation process as seen from the perspective of the product life cycle. The core of innovation management is examined, along with the most detailed roles and responsibilities that managers must fulfill when carrying out managerial duties.

Keywords: *development, management, innovation, enterprise, economy.*

Introduction

The accelerated rate of technological development and a number of megatrends have an impact on the innovation process and the function of innovation managers within the company. Its primary objective is to assign the enterprise's scientific-technical and production vectors to the following areas: developing and introducing new or enhanced products. International standards define innovation as the end outcome of innovation activity, which might take the shape of a newly developed or improved product that is launched to the market, a new technological method that is applied to real-world activities, or a new strategy for providing services. For a firm to become more competitive and break free from reliance on variations in the "quality loop," the development and implementation of a new product into production is crucial.

This topic of the article is relevant because today in a shaky position is the innovation management system, on which, in fact, depends mechanism of organizational and economic management of the national economy. In the modern market, innovations are designed to contribute to the accelerated formation economy, ensure intensive implementation of the latest developments obtained thanks to science and technology. Innovation is necessary to meet needs consumers through the release of a variety of high-quality products and providing completely new services.

By using advances in production, this ought to be guaranteed. The creation, dissemination, and use of a novel, workable solution to a novel or current problem constitute innovation. Innovation is defined as something that is introduced or in use that improves the quality of processes or goods that are in demand in the market. When we discuss innovation, we are referring to a product that has been profitably brought into production through research and development (R&D) and has been effectively introduced.

This development after opening it is qualitatively superior to the previous model or is a completely new product (service). The process of consistently turning an idea into goods going through the stages of fundamental and applied research, design development, marketing, production and sales is defined as an innovation process, and the period of development, diffusion and exploitation of an innovation is called the innovation cycle.

Main Part

The process of innovation encompasses all corporate activities, ranging from scientific research and marketing to the sale, operation, and disposal of new products. This allows a variety of businesses and business structures to compete in the innovation market. Conversely, the goal of strategic innovation management is to use the innovation process to directly produce future results. Despite the consistent innovation focus, a range of organizational and economic circumstances contribute to the uniqueness of each innovation in innovation activity.

Classification of innovations.

The distinctions between incremental and radical innovations can be seen in the qualitative differences in the degree of novelty of new goods and services. They also show how dependent modification (improving) innovations are on radical innovations; the latter act as a springboard for additional improvements, but their staged implementations encounter opposition from modifying innovations. When creating novel goods or services, an inventor or innovation manager must pay close attention to the distinctive aspects of the innovation process. We can be persuaded once more of the diversity processes, their nature, organizational structures, scale, and means of impacting inventive activity thanks to this categorization of inventions.

By importance in economic development and by degree of novelty distinguish:

- *basic* – innovations that implement major inventions that become the basis for the formation of new generations and directions in engineering and technology. They belong to fundamentally new products;

- *improving* – innovations that implement small and medium-sized inventions that contribute to the spread and stability of the development of scientific and technological progress. They concern significant improvements in existing products and production methods;

- *pseudo-innovations* - innovations aimed at partial improvement through modernization and rationalization of outdated equipment (technology) and acting (mainly) as a brake on technical progress.

According to technological characteristics, innovations are divided into:

- *product* – innovations aimed at using new materials and semi-finished products, components, to obtain fundamentally new products;

- *process* innovations are innovations manifested in new technology production, in new methods of work production, at a higher level automation, in new methods of organizing production and management.

According to the type of novelty for the market, innovations can be:

- 1) new, for the industry in the world;
- 2) new, in the country, region;
- 3) new, for an innovative enterprise.

The main point of innovation management

The process of continuously improving a company's performance metrics, including any positive ones like technology and technical execution and knowledge management, is known as innovation management. The needs of customers are intimately linked to the introduction of innovations. The innovator ascertains which products are necessary for the market, which ones need to be improved, and which works and services can fully fill the intended segment of the market. In other words, in a competitive setting, it seeks the best way to boost the productivity of innovative potential businesses.

Innovation managers' tasks include coming up with unconventional solutions to unusual problems, making fast and accurate assessments of the state of the goods (or services) market, and determining which course of action will give their organization a competitive edge.

Innovation management is one of the types of professional activities that are aimed at achieving specific innovative goals company operating in a market economy, optimal results based on the rational use of scientific, material, financial and labor resources, application of various principles, methods and functions economic management mechanism. The innovation manager faces process of activity with calculations, indicators and forecasts that take into account specifics of innovation activity. Innovation management relates to various types of innovation activities and, based on specific indicators, focuses on the implementation management activities. The functions of this type of management are:

- 1) Based on market conditions, as well as changes in the external environment, observed corrective impacts of innovation goals;
- 2) In the process of making management decisions, modern bases are used for multivariate calculations;
- 3) The planned end result of the company's innovative activities as achievement orientation;
- 4) Current goals of strategic management and planning are undergoing changes to the future;
- 5) In the process of assessing work management, only realistic final results achieved;
- 6) All scientific, technical and production potential;
- 7) Anticipating change and developing flexible solutions as the basis for implementation management;
- 8) Each segment of the company's work is provided with innovations, innovations;
- 9) Each economic decision is subject to deep economic analysis. Innovation managers in the course of their professional activities solve a number of problems, including:
 - 1) Determine the goals of strategic development and management of the company;
 - 2) Identify priority tasks, as well as the sequence of their implementation;
 - 3) Manage changes in the company;
 - 4) Develop company development strategies - economic tasks and ways to achieve them solutions;
 - 5) Prepare activities for the development and development of new products;
 - 6) Assess the necessary resources and search for their sources provision;
 - 7) Provide strict control over the implementation of the formulated tasks;
 - 8) Predict the results of the company's development based on impact observable factors;

- 9) Ensure the viability of their company in competitive conditions;
- 10) Strive to achieve maximum profit in established economic conditions;
- 11) Constantly improve all the work of the company, using the most modern management methods;
- 12) Prepare necessary innovations in advance;
- 13) Improve the organizational structure of the enterprise based on changing requirements;
- 14) Ensure the effective work of each employee, both individually and the team as a whole, accepting it as a single interacting system;
- 15) Systematically develop and implement more advanced technologies at the enterprise forms of entrepreneurship, penetrating into new areas of business.

Conclusion

Innovation management uses its own economic mechanism and is directly related to the methodology of scientific management. The economic mechanism of management is objectively determined by the company's work in conditions of a market economy, when the results of the activities of the entire enterprise receive market valuation.

The structure of business management and the decision-making process are fundamental to the idea of "innovation management." Owing to the peculiarities of innovation, it is considered that an innovation manager is a unique kind of person. Together with the fundamental qualifications (creativity and analytical skills), the manager also needs to be knowledgeable about innovation in the production sector, the state of the market for investments and innovations, organizational skills in the field of innovation (creation and development of new types of products), services, and specific works; comprehend and execute financial and economic evaluations of innovation and production endeavors; comprehend the fundamentals of labor relations and employee incentives, legal statutes and forms of governmental assistance, etc. Ensuring the proper functioning of entities and making more efficient use of resources are the ultimate goals of innovation management.

The process of introducing new technologies can be challenging. Many individuals think that labor expenses and the labor share in recalculating the cost of a unit of production decrease as technology means improve. Because it necessitates the development and application of progressively costly lines, robotics, industrial equipment, etc.

Both the cost of environmental preservation and the overall cost of modernization are rising. The expense of depreciation and maintenance of used fixed assets now accounts for a larger portion of the production cost. The company's competitiveness and ability to stay in the market, however, primarily depend on how openly product manufacturers are to technological and engineering advancements that make it possible to produce and market high-quality goods while making the best use of available resources.

Economic efficiency and the life cycle of the product are the two factors that innovators (or those who create innovations) follow. Their primary approach is to develop an innovation that is acknowledged as being exceptional in a certain field, outperforming rivals in the process.

References:

1. Hossain, M. Adopting open innovation to stimulate frugal innovation and reverse innovation / M. Hossain // SSRN Electronic Journal. doi:10.2139/ssrn.2197782 [Electronic resource]. – 2013. – Mode of access: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/256044169_Adopting_Open_Innovation_to_Stimulate_Frugal_Innovation_and_Reverse_Innovation. – Date of access: 2022.
2. Sven Irmer. Innovation management as part of the general management of the organization. International Journal of Advanced Engineering and Management Research Vol. 2 Issue 6, 2017
3. Инновационный менеджмент: учеб.пособие/С.Д.Ильенкова и др.- М.,2008
4. Инновационный менеджмент: электронный учебно-методический

комплекс для специальности: 1-26 02 02-08 «Менеджмент (инновационный)». В 2 ч. Ч. 1. Основы инновационного менеджмента /БГУ Экономический фак., Каф. инноватики и предпринимательской деятельности ; сост. О. Ю. Жуковская. – Минск : БГУ, 2022. – 105 с. : ил. – Библиогр.: с. 97–105.

5. Недюхина, О. М. Инновационный менеджмент. Курс лекций : учебнометодическое пособие / О. М. Недюхина, Е. В. Кокиц. – Горки : БГСХА, 2021. – 133 с. ISBN 978-985-882-181-4.

